

Comparison of Haemoglobin Level in Postpartum Anaemic Patients Receiving Intravenous Iron Sucrose and Intravenous Ferric Carboxymaltose

Geddamm Swarupa¹, Anusha Rani M V², Chodavarapu Sailaja³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Government Medical College, Rajamahendravaram, East Godavari district, AP

²Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences, Karimnagar, Telangana

³Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Government Medical College, Rajamahendravaram, East Godavari District, AP

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Anusha Rani

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: WHO defined postpartum anaemia as Haemoglobin level of <10gm% during postpartum period. The prevalence of postpartum anaemia is high and it ranges from 4 to 27% .In developing countries higher prevalence, 50-80% has been reported. Prevalence of postpartum anaemia at 6 weeks has been quoted as 70% in India.

Aim and Objectives: To compare the Haemoglobin levels in Postpartum Anaemia patients receiving I.V Iron sucrose and I.V Ferric carboxymaltose.

Material and Methods: A prospective open labelled study was conducted at Government Maternity Hospital, Petlaburz after the approval from Institutional Ethics Committee. The study included 100 patients diagnosed with post-partum anaemia. The patients were divided into 2 groups .Each group included 50 patients. Group I received I.V iron sucrose 1000mg on alternate days till the required dose is completed. Group II received I.V Ferric Carboxymaltose once in a week. In both groups Haemoglobin levels done before treatment and 2 weeks after the treatment.

Observation and Results: On comparing both groups using student t test, we found that increase in Haemoglobin concentration and serum ferritin level in group receiving Ferric Carboxymaltose was found statistically significant over Iron sucrose group.

Conclusion: In this study, administration of ferric carboxymaltose increased the haemoglobin level more rapidly as compared to iron sucrose in women with Iron deficiency anaemia in post-partum period. Ferric carboxymaltose is well tolerated, safe and effective alternative to blood transfusion in the treatment of iron deficiency anaemia in the post-partum period.

Keywords: Postpartum Anaemia, Haemoglobin, Ferric Carboxymaltose (FCM), Iron Sucrose (IS).

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Most common nutritional deficiency in the world is Anaemia. 1.62 billion people are affected globally, which constitute 24.8% of the total population and majority of individuals affected are pregnant women among them. As defined by WHO, anaemia is haemoglobin less than 11gm% and is the commonest cause of maternal morbidity and mortality especially in the developing countries. Most common cause of postpartum anaemia is Iron deficiency .The rate is as high as 50%, reported in the first week of postpartum [1] (Asma et al., 2014). WHO defined postpartum anaemia as the Haemoglobin level < 10 g% during the period of post-partum [2]. The prevalence of postpartum

anaemia is high and the range of postpartum anaemia is 4% to 27% [3]. Higher prevalence of 50-80% has been reported in developing countries. The prevalence of postpartum anaemia at 6 weeks has been quoted as 70% [4] in India. Oral iron therapy, parenteral iron and blood transfusion are the modalities of treatment for postpartum anaemia. Though oral iron is widely used for treatment for iron deficiency anaemia (IDA), not all patients respond adequately to oral iron. Oral iron has side effects, predominantly gastrointestinal discomfort leading to lack of efficacy and poor compliance. Parenteral iron preparations like iron dextran sometimes has been associated with serious side

effects. (Rodolfo et al., 2011) Therefore iron dextran was not utilized. Iron sucrose complex which was developed later has offered better compliance and tolerance. Iron sucrose complex has a better safety profile but multidosing of Iron sucrose has been remained as an issue.[5] Many other compounds like iron dextran(IM/IV), iron sorbitol (IM), iron sucrose (IV), ferric carboxymaltose etc are available for parenteral therapy. Among them iron sucrose and ferric carboxymaltose give better results .The iron in iron sucrose and ferric carboxymaltose bind quickly to transferrin and also travel quickly to bone marrow. This results in early rise in Haemoglobin [6].Iron sucrose and ferric carboxymaltose are safe in postpartum period. Both these compounds have less chances of hypersensitivity reactions (Test dose is not required) [7].

Materials and Methods

Prospective open labelled study was conducted at Govt. Maternity Hospital, Petlaburz, which included 100 patients with postpartum anaemia 50 in each group.

Group A: 50 patients received I.V iron sucrose according to the dose required and till the dose is reached. It is given by an infusion of 200mg diluted in 200 ml of normal saline over 20 to 30 min every alternate day till required dose is completed. Maximum of 600 mg iron sucrose was given per week .Total dose is 1000mg.

Group B: 50 patients receiving IV Ferric Carboxymaltose by infusion of 1000mg in 250 ml of Normal saline over 15 minutes.

Follow up: All the two groups were followed after two weeks and complete haemogram and serum ferritin was done.

Ethical Consideration:

The study was conducted after the approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee and informed consent from the patients.

Duration of Study: 1 ½ year

Inclusion Criteria:

- Postpartum women between the age of 18 to 35 years with haemoglobin level <10g/dl.
- Women with iron deficiency anaemia only

Exclusion Criteria:

- Anaemia other than iron deficiency
- Patient allergic or intolerant to iron derivatives
- Patients with known history of asthma, thromboembolism, seizure disorders
- Patients with signs of infection
- Evidence of renal or hepatic dysfunction
- Anaemia due to renal diseases and inflammatory bowel diseases

Statistical Analysis: Firstly descriptive statistics was used to calculate the mean +/- SD. Independent student t test was used to compare the means of parameters of both the groups. A 95% limit and 5% level of significance was adopted.

Therefore p value less than 0.05 is considered significant. Statistical analysis was performed using the SPSS software package for windows version 22.0) Master chart was prepared and analysis was done.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Comparisons of peripheral smear between the groups

Peripheral Smear	Frequency (%)		Total	Chi-square	P-value
	Group A	Group B			
MCHC	29(58.0%)	31(62%)	60(60%)	1.092	0.579 (Not Significant)
MCNC	1(2%)	0(0%)	1(1%)		
NCNC	20(40%)	19(38%)	39(39%)		
Total	50(100%)	50(100%)	100(100%)		

There is no significant difference in peripheral smear between the groups.

Table 2: Comparison of mean antenatal Hb in both groups.

Antenatal Hb	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Group A	50	9.314	0.6863	0.001
Group B	50	8.722	0.446	

The mean Hb in group A and group B showing significant difference showing the p value of 0.001

Table 3: Comparison of Haemoglobin percentage pre-treatment and post treatment

Haemoglobin	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P Value
Pre Treatment	A	50	8.046	0.421	0.044
	B	50	7.864	0.4715	
Post Treatment	A	50	9.714	0.4375	0.001
	B	50	10.826	0.4275	

Table 4: Comparison of mean Hb between the groups

HB (PND15-PND0)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-value
Group A	50	1.668	0.2986	0.001
Group B	50	2.962	0.2586	

Table 5: Comparison of LCB between the groups.

LCB	N	Mean	S.D	p value
Group A	50	1.38	1.2271	0.603
Group B	50	1.5	1.069	

Table 6: Comparison of pre and post transfusion ferritin

	Group	N	Mean	S.D	p value
Pre trans ferritin	A	50	56.04	6.74	0.695
	B	50	55.52	6.4626	
Post trans ferritin	A	50	175.4	6.3535	0.001
	B	50	289.94	6.7443	

Table 7: Comparison of Mean serum ferritin after transfusion between the groups.

Ferritin (Pre-Post)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Group A	50	119.36	2.2293	0.001
Group B	50	234.42	3.3447	

Mean increase of serum ferritin 119.3 in group A and 234.420 in group B with significant p value of 0.001.

Discussion

Anaemia is one of the most common causes of disability. It is the major global public health problem. In spite of awareness of anaemia in iron deficiency among pregnant women, not much attention is paid to correct it and even there is less scrutiny towards postpartum anaemia. The aim of treatment of postpartum anaemia is to increase the level of Haemoglobin in serum by 2.4 to 4.6 gm %. Ferric carboxymaltose is non-dextran iron complex. It consists of a ferric hydroxide core which is stabilised by a carbohydrate shell. This design of macromolecular ferric hydroxide carbohydrate complex permits guarded delivery of iron to the cells of the reticuloendothelial system. Subsequently iron is thus delivered to the iron binding proteins, ferritin and transferrin, with negligible risk of large amounts of ionic iron being released in to serum. Being a non-dextran molecule and also having very low immunogenic potential, it is thus not predisposed to high risk of reactions of anaphylaxis. Therefore these properties allow the administration of large doses in a single and rapid session. Test dose is not required. Thus it makes ferric carboxymaltose suitable as first choice for the treatment of iron deficiency anaemia.

In our study both Ferric Carboxymaltose and Iron sucrose are effective in improving Hb concentration and replenishment of iron stores in postpartum anaemic patients. Both groups are compared using independent student t test. We found that increase in Hb concentration and serum ferritin levels in FCM group was found statistically significant over IS group with p value 0.001. On

comparison of Mean Haemoglobin percentage, pre and post treatment in both groups, it improved from 8.04g % to 9.7g % i.e., 1.7g % increase in 2 weeks in Group A and in Group B Hb, it increased from 7.8g% to 10.81g % i.e. increase of 3g %. On Comparing mean Hb in both groups on postnatal day 15, Group A showed an increase of 1.6gm % and Group B showed an increase of 2.962g % and the p value was 0.001 which is statistically significant. Mean of pre and post transfusion serum ferritin in Group A is 119.360 and Group B is 234.4, which showed statistical significance. So in the present study, there is significant rise in Haemoglobin and Serum ferritin in Group B. Thus, we conclude that FCM is more efficacious than IV iron sucrose.

The study showed that there was an increase of 2.52 gm/dl in haemoglobin level after 2 weeks of therapy and mean haemoglobin level was 8.66 gm/dl in Group A. In Group B there was an increase of 1.95 gm/dl in haemoglobin level and the haemoglobin level was 8.01 gm/dl at 2 weeks after therapy. This difference further increased at 4 weeks after therapy. The haemoglobin level was 10.01 gm/dl in Group A (rise of 3.95 gm/dl) at 4 weeks of therapy and in Group B haemoglobin level was 9.38 gm/dl (rise of 3.32 gm/dl). Mean haematological parameters increased significantly after 4 weeks in FCM group and iron sucrose group. We compared the improvement of mean haematological parameter which is more in Group A than Group B after 4 weeks of iron therapy. In group A, 84% cases achieved the target haemoglobin at 8 weeks after therapy and 100% cases achieved target haemoglobin at 12 weeks after therapy. In Group B, 80% cases achieved the target haemoglobin at 8 weeks after therapy and 98% cases achieved target haemoglobin at 12

weeks after therapy. In Group A, 92% cases were completely relieved of their symptoms at 4 weeks after therapy and in Group B only 84% cases were completely relieved of their symptoms. So, we can say that the intravenous iron carboxymaltose therapy is more effective therapy to treat iron deficiency anaemia during postpartum period. In a study conducted by Breyman et al in postpartum period, the increase in mean Hb was 3.37 g/dl in FCM group and 3.29 g/dl in ferrous sulphate group after 12 weeks of iron therapy [8]

In a study conducted by Seid et al in postpartum women, the group who received FCM, achieved target haemoglobin (>12 gm%) which is in higher when compared to iron sucrose after 6 weeks of iron therapy. Study conducted by Von Wyck et al has shown that increase in Haemoglobin is greater than or equal to 2 gm/dl in the group who received FCM when compared to the group that received oral iron; after 6 weeks of iron therapy. In a study conducted by Seid et al it was found that FCM was better than oral iron in increasing the iron stores, which was measured by ferritin and transferrin saturations which indicate the amount of iron available for erythropoiesis. They found that one course of FCM replenished the iron stores at maximum.

Conclusion

Administration of Intravenous Ferric carboxymaltose increased the haemoglobin level more rapidly when compared to iron sucrose in women with iron deficiency anaemia in the postpartum period. It also restores iron more rapidly. The mean haemoglobin level achieved in intravenous Ferric carboxymaltose group was significantly higher and the rate of increase in haemoglobin level was also significantly higher in intravenous iron carboxymaltose group. The number of cases achieving target haemoglobin was significantly higher in the group who received intravenous ferric carboxymaltose. Out of the two different IV iron preparations used in this study, FCM proved to be statistically better than iron sucrose

Ferric carboxymaltose elevates haemoglobin level and restores iron stores faster than iron sucrose and oral iron. The overall satisfaction reported by the patients was better as they received the drug with minimum hospital stay in a single dose (within 15 min). It takes 3 months to replenish iron stores. With oral iron therapy. Intravenous iron sucrose requires multiple doses but single dose of FCM is sufficient to replenish the iron stores. Postpartum anaemia is widespread in India. National health authorities should establish guidelines to combat

iron deficiency in pregnancy and postpartum, thereby decreasing the maternal mortality, morbidity, and infant morbidity, in order to facilitate a prosperous future for both mothers and children in a continuing globalized world. Thus, we can conclude that intravenous iron carboxymaltose is convenient, more effective and faster acting than intravenous iron sucrose therapy for the treatment of iron deficiency anaemia during postpartum period.

Clinical Significance: When compared with oral therapy and blood transfusions, this total drug infusion concept with third-generation parenteral iron molecules is convenient for the patient and it can also save the resources in health care system. IV FCM may be considered early, while treating patient with postpartum anaemia because of properties like ultrashort duration of treatment, no hospitalization being required and quicker replenishing of iron stores.

References

1. Asma A. Jalwadi AI and AI Deen H. Postnatal maternal morbidity: Causes and predictors. *Medical Journal of Babylon*. 2014; 2(3).
2. Kausar S, Malik M, Malik A et al., safety and efficacy of intravenous iron therapy in postnatal patients with iron deficiency anaemia. *J South Asian Fed Obstet Gynaecol*. 2011;3:25-7
3. Milman N. Postpartum anemia I: definition, prevalence, causes, and consequences. *Annals of Hematology*. 2011; 90(11): 1247-53.
4. Somdatta P, Reddaiah VP and Singh B. Prevalence of anaemia in the postpartum period: A study of a North Indian Village. *Tropical Doctor*. 2009; 39(4): 211-5.
5. Agarwal S, Gupta M et al. Evaluation of iron sucrose for postpartum anaemia, *International Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*. 2013; 3(2): 208-211.
6. Christian Breyman. The Use of iron sucrose complex for anaemia in pregnancy and the postpartum period. *Semin Hematol*. 2006;43 (Suppl 6): S 28-31.
7. Mukherji J. Iron deficiency anemia in pregnancy. *Rational Drug Bulletin*. 2002;12 :25.
8. Bentley DP. Iron metabolism and anaemia in pregnancy. In: Letsky EA, editor. *Clinics in Haematology*. London: WB Saunders; 1985; 14:613-28.
9. Breyman C, Gilga F, Bejenariu C, Stirzhova N. Comparative efficacy and safety of intravenous Ferric carboxymaltose in the treatment of iron deficiency anaemia. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2008;101: 67-73.